

Magic Graphs and Related Problems

Fangming Li

fangming4875@yandex.com

Independent Researcher, China

October 8, 2025

Abstract: This article presents two original magic labellings: one based on the trihexagonal tiling, discovered in my childhood, and another inspired by the Sengso Magic Tower puzzle. Both of them reveal the harmony between numbers and shapes. Possible extensions and open problems are introduced, together with reflections on the aesthetic and playful nature of mathematics and its value in education.

Keywords: magic labelling, trihexagonal tiling, Sengso Magic Tower, recreational mathematics, mathematical beauty

1 Introduction

I was not especially interested in mathematics until my father taught me the classic 3×3 magic square: filling a 3×3 square grid with the integers 1 to 9 so that each row, column and diagonal sums to 15. I was astonished at the harmony between numbers and shapes, and soon became fascinated with mathematical games, even inventing some of my own. I explored how numbers can be arranged on shapes beyond square grids, such as on trihexagonal tilings and polyhedra, so that they satisfy similar properties. Through this exploration, I discovered several new kinds of “magic” graphs. Some of these arrangements appear to be new, and I hope they may stimulate further investigation. I shall present them in this article.

2 A Magic Graph Based on the Trihexagonal Tiling

Magic labelling puzzles often ask whether it is possible to assign numbers to the vertices of a graph so that certain sums are the same throughout. In some cases, however, the sums in the graph involve different numbers of terms, and it may then be more natural to require different common sums. For example, regular triangles and hexagons can tessellate the plane, forming what is known as the *trihexagonal tiling*. When I was in primary school, I discovered a magic graph based on part of this tiling (see Figure 1), in which the three

numbers on each triangular face sum to 42, while the six numbers on each hexagonal face sum to 84. It is interesting to note that 84 is twice 42, just as 6 is twice 3.

Figure 1: The magic labelling I discovered in childhood, based on part of the trihexagonal tiling.

I have not yet found any universally applicable method or algorithm for constructing this magic labelling. Nor have I discovered a formal proof explaining why the common sums should be 42 and 84. Instead, I completed the labelling largely by intuition and experimentation. The numbers 13, 14, and 15 are those lying at the centre of the range from 1 to 27, so I chose their total, 42, to be the common sum for each unit triangle, and placed them on the central triangle of the figure. Since a hexagon has twice as many vertices as a triangle, I let the common sum for the hexagons be twice 42.

Moreover, I felt that if I distributed numbers of similar size in different directions across the graph, it might be easier to achieve a successful arrangement. More specifically, one may notice that the magic labelling satisfies a pleasing property:

For any a, b, c of the form $3n + 1, 3n + 2, 3n + 3$ (with $n = 0, \dots, 8$) — for example, 1, 2, 3 or 7, 8, 9 — the point labelled a (respectively b) in the figure moves to the position originally occupied by b (respectively c) under a rotation of 120° anticlockwise about the centre of the diagram. (*)

As a result, any such three numbers form the vertices of an equilateral triangle when joined by straight line segments (see Figure 2). As I placed the remaining numbers on the diagram, I kept checking that the local sums matched my expectations. In the end, I was pleasantly surprised that the construction worked.

It is well known that the classical 3×3 magic square has essentially only one solution: any two solutions can be obtained from each other by rotation or reflection. Thus, operations such as a 90° rotation are called *automorphisms* of the magic square, since they preserve all the triples of numbers that give the required sum.

Figure 2: Two equilateral triangles formed by joining the triples $(1, 2, 3)$ and $(16, 17, 18)$, respectively.

Similarly, operations such as a 120° rotation and the reflection about the vertical line of symmetry act as automorphisms of the magic graph described here. There is, however, another type of automorphism: if we exchange the numbers 1 and 26, 2 and 27, or 3 and 25, then the resulting labelling is essentially the same, because the triples and sexuples producing the target sums remain unchanged.

Hence one may ask: up to rotation, reflection, and the interchange of two corner numbers, how many distinct solutions are there? If we further require the labelling to satisfy Property (*), then reflections and corner interchanges are no longer automorphisms, and we may ask again: how many solutions exist up to the remaining automorphisms?

The trihexagonal tiling can extend indefinitely on the plane. So for larger portions of the tiling, that is, those containing more triangles or hexagons, and for regions of different shapes, such as those illustrated in Figure 3, do corresponding magic labellings exist? And if so, what are the answers to the questions raised above? I leave these as open problems for the interested reader.

Figure 3: Examples of larger or differently shaped portions of the trihexagonal tiling.

3 A Magic Labelling Inspired by the 3×3 Sengso Magic Tower

The 3×3 *Sengso Magic Tower* is a puzzle similar to the Rubik's Cube, but with the shape of a tetrahedron (see Figure 4 for a picture of the puzzle). Each face is an equilateral triangle, divided by three internal lines passing through it. Let us consider the following question:

We call a line *significant* if it is either an edge of the tetrahedron or one of these internal lines. Altogether there are 18 such lines on the surface of the tower. Their intersections, including the four corner points of the tetrahedron, form 28 distinct vertices. Each significant line passes through four vertices. Hence, is it possible to assign the integers $1, 2, \dots, 28$ to these vertices so that the four numbers on every significant line have the same total?

Figure 4: A 3×3 Sengso Magic Tower.

I have not yet found a formal proof determining what the common sum should be. Instead, guided by intuition, I observed that 13, 14, 15, and 16 lie at the centre of the range from 1 to 28, and I therefore took their total, 58, as the common sum. After expressing these conditions as a system of linear equations, I sought the help of *OpenAI's ChatGPT*, which acted as a reasoning assistant, to find a labelling satisfying all constraints. The resulting configuration is shown in Figure 5, which is a planar net of the tetrahedron. Any two points representing the same vertex in three dimensions are joined by dotted curves and carry identical labels.

A natural question to ask is how many distinct solutions exist, up to rotation and reflection. The problem may also be extended in another direction: for the surfaces of other twisty puzzles, do similar magic labellings exist? For instance, the *Megaminx* is a dodecahedral puzzle, each of whose faces has the structure shown in Figure 6. We can define significant lines and vertices in the same way as before: all edges of the dodecahe-

Figure 5: A planar representation of a magic labelling on the 3×3 Sengso Magic Tower.

dron and internal lines drawn across faces are taken to be significant lines. This network consists of 90 lines and 140 vertices in total. Hence, can the integers $1, 2, \dots, 140$ be assigned to these vertices so that every significant line has the same sum? And if so, how many such labellings exist up to automorphism? I leave these questions to the interested reader.

Figure 6: The structure of a single face of the Megaminx.

4 Conclusion

In this article, I have presented two magic labellings — one based on the trihexagonal tiling, discovered in my childhood, and another inspired by the Sengso Magic Tower puzzle. Through these examples, we can glimpse some of the beauty and mystery of

mathematics — qualities that have long inspired my love for the subject.

Beyond the specific puzzles introduced here and consequent problems, a broader question also arises: should we bring more of the playful and artistic spirit of mathematics into mathematics education? Many people grow up fearing or disliking mathematics, perhaps because their first encounters with it emphasised only its technical side, rather than its elegance and creativity. Yet mathematics is far more than formulas and equations: it is also an art to be appreciated, and a game to be enjoyed. If students could experience mathematics in this spirit, they might well feel far more motivated to explore it deeply.

Acknowledgements: I would like to thank OpenAI’s ChatGPT (version GPT-5) for assisting in verifying calculations, improving the grammar and clarity of the manuscript, and generating Figure 4 for illustration. All mathematical ideas and formulations are my own. The solution to the Sengso Magic Tower problem was obtained with computational assistance from ChatGPT.

Declaration of Interest Statement: There are no competing interests to declare.

Funding: No funding was received for the preparation of this article.